

Psychometric Analysis of PICSE Framework

1 BACKGROUND

Johnson et al. [8] interviewed software engineers to identify factors influencing trust in tools, culminating in the PICSE framework (Table 1): (1) *Personal* (internal, external, and social factors), (2) *Interaction* (engagement aspects), (3) *Control* (over the tool), (4) *System* (properties of the tool), and (5) *Expectations* (from the tool). Since PICSE is developed for software engineering (SE), we use it to design our survey instrument to identify factors influencing developers’ trust in genAI tools. As PICSE was developed qualitatively, its psychometric quality—reliability and validity—of a survey derived from it must be empirically evaluated.

Below, we present the psychometric analysis of the PICSE framework (also reported in our recent work [1]), contributing a validated instrument for capturing relevant factors developers consider when forming trust in genAI tools.

2 METHOD

Psychometric quality [9, 12] refers to the objectivity, reliability, and validity of an instrument. We primarily used validated instruments in designing the survey. However, since PICSE was not validated, we conducted a psychometric analysis to empirically refine its factor groupings, which were then evaluated for their association with trust. Table 1 presents the factors evaluated in our survey. We performed the analysis using the JASP tool [7], adhering to established psychometric procedures [5, 11, 12] as detailed next:

Table 1: PICSE framework [8]

Category	Items
Personal	Community (P1), Source reputation (P2), Clear advantages (P3)
Interaction	Output validation support (I1), Feedback loop (I2), Educational value (I3)
Control	Control over output use (C1), Ease of workflow integration (C2)
System	Ease of use (S1), Polished presentation (S2), Safe and secure practices (S3), Consistent accuracy and appropriateness (S4), Performance (S5)
Expectations	Meeting expectations (E1), Transparent data practices (E2), Style matching (E3), Goal maintenance (E4)

We dropped C3 (tool ownership), as it pertained to AI engineers developing parts of genAI models.

1) Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) – Original grouping:

CFA is a statistical technique that examines intercorrelations between items and proposed factors to test whether a set of observed variables align with a pre-determined factor structure [4]. We assessed whether the PICSE items align with their original five-factor structure (Personal, Interaction, Control, System, and Expectations). The model fit was evaluated using multiple indices: Chi-square test, Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), Standardized Root Mean-squared Residual (SRMR), Comparative Fit Index (CFI), and Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI) [6]. Indications of a good model fit

include $RMSEA < .06$, $SRMR \leq .08$, and $0.95 \leq CFI, TLI \leq 1$ [6]. We employed a robust maximum likelihood estimator (MLE)¹, since the data did not meet multivariate normality assumptions, confirmed using Mardia’s test [10] (Table 4). As shown in Table 3, results from the original five-factor structure did not indicate a good model fit based on RMSEA, SRMR, CFI, and TLI. This was not entirely unexpected given PICSE’s conceptual nature [4]. Therefore, to identify a more appropriate model of factors, we proceeded with an exploratory factor analysis (EFA), uncovering alternative groupings that might better fit the data.

Table 2: EFA: Factor loadings and communalities (h2)

Item	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4	Factor 5	h2
S2	0.655					0.525
S3	0.729					0.609
S4	0.823					0.623
S5	0.638					0.657
E3	0.614					0.559
I3		0.941				0.779
P3		0.791				0.599
S1			0.739			0.668
C2			0.671			0.607
P1				0.613		0.418
P2				0.539		0.367
C1				0.517		0.312
E4					0.628	0.685
I1						0.398
I2						0.481
E1						0.405
E2						0.492

The applied oblique rotation method is promax. Community values (h2)<0.5 are problematic [2] and are marked in RED. Items loaded well (>0.5) onto their primary factors without cross-loadings (>0.3) onto other factors [3]; hence their corresponding cells are kept blank.

2) *Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)*: Unlike CFA, which relies on an existing a priori expectation of factor structures, EFA identifies the suitable number of latent constructs (factors) and underlying factor structures without imposing a preconceived model [5]. Given the violation of multivariate normality, we used principal axis factoring (considering factors with eigenvalues > 1), as recommended for EFA [5]. We employed oblique rotation, anticipating correlations among the factors. The data met EFA assumptions: significant Bartlett’s test for sphericity ($\chi^2(136) = 1633.97, p < .001$) and an adequate Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test (0.892, recommended $\geq .60$) [5]. We used both parallel analysis and a scree plot to determine the number of factors [5], suggesting an alternate five-factor model explaining 64.6% of the total variance. However, most of this variance (60.3%) was accounted for by factors 1, 2, 3, and 5 (22.7, 15.1, 10.6, and 11.9% respectively), while factor 4 explained only 4.3%. The factors showed low correlations (0.2-0.3), except for factor 4,

¹Robust maximum likelihood estimation adjusts for non-normality in data. In general, “robust” in factor analyses refers to methods and values resilient to deviations from ideal distributional assumptions.

which had high correlations with factors 2 (0.625) and 3 (0.524) (see supplemental). Table 2 presents the factor loadings, which indicate the extent to which changes in the underlying factor are reflected in the corresponding indicator (item). All items loaded well onto their factors with primary loadings > 0.5 (items with loadings below 0.4 should be excluded) [3]. For interpreting communality (i.e., the proportion of an item’s variance explained by the common factors in factor analyses), values < 0.5 are considered problematic and not interpretable [2]. As shown in Table 2, the communality values for items I1, I2, E1, and E2 were below 0.5, and as they did not load onto any of the factors, they were excluded from the final model. Items in factor 4 (P1, P2, C1) also had low communality values and were likewise dismissed. Based on these results, we concluded that a four-factor solution was the most appropriate, dropping factor 4 due to its low variance explanation, high correlations with other factors, and low communality. The fit indices in Table 3 indicate a good model fit, showing that the EFA factor structure better fits the data than the original PICSE grouping in the above CFA analysis.

Table 3: Model Fit Indices - PICSE Psychometric Evaluation

Model	RMSEA	SRMR	CFI	TLI	χ^2	p-val
CFA-Original	0.104	0.084	0.925	0.927	147.3	<0.01
EFA	0.057	0.054	0.968	0.965	109.1	<0.01
CFA-Alternate	0.048	0.047	0.982	0.973	59.0	<0.01

χ^2 test results were not considered, as the test is affected by deviations from multivariate normality [13]. We still report the values for completeness.

3) **CFA - Alternate grouping:** In the final step, as is best practice [12], we conducted CFA to validate the factor structure identified through EFA. The CFA fit indices in Table 3 confirm the EFA-derived four-factor model (RMSEA = 0.048; SRMR = 0.047, CFI = 0.982, TLI = 0.973). Table 2 outlines the factor structure and corresponding item groupings. Factor 1, labeled **System/Output quality**, includes items S2 through S5 and E3, which relate to the System group (in PICSE) and the style matching of genAI’s outputs. Factor 2, labeled **Functional value**, encompasses items I3 and P3, reflecting the educational value and practical advantages of using genAI tools. Factor 3, labeled **Ease of use**, comprises items S1 and C2, addressing the ease of using and integrating genAI in the workflow. Factor 5, labeled **Goal maintenance**, includes a single item, E4, focusing on genAI’s maintenance of human goals. The reliability and validity assessments further support the robustness of these constructs (see Sec. 5: RQ1&2 Results in the manuscript).

In summary, the psychometric analysis confirmed that a four-factor solution is most appropriate and provided a validated measurement instrument for capturing these factors.

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Table 4: Mardia’s Test of Multivariate Normality

	Value	Statistic	df	p
Skewness	61.573	1446.967	969	< .001
Small Sample Skewness	61.573	1481.231	969	< .001
Kurtosis	350.654	6.46	-	< .001

Skewness statistic is assumed to be χ^2 distributed, and that for kurtosis is standard normal. The sample does not meet assumptions for multivariate normality.

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